

Irish Association for Documentation 1947-?

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Introduction

In early 2026, I was going through archival materials related to the documentation movement in the interwar years and the immediate postwar period. In the meeting minutes of the Information Services Committee of the Royal Society in February 1949, I noted the following:

“Irish Association on Documentation: A letter had been received from Professor F. E. Hackett who was the delegate of Eire to the Conference, stating that an Association had been formed in Eire which will co-operate in any matters by this Committee.”

The Irish Association for Documentation certainly no longer exists. Its history, however, has not yet been written. In fact, no one had heard about the Association when I inquired with my academic and professional colleagues. My research interest in the documentation movement means that I could not miss this important development in a country where I live and work. Hence, I moved to consult the materials available and I browsed issues of *An Leabharlann* published between 1930-1982 for traces about this seemingly mysterious association. This article presents some preliminary findings to spark interest in further studies about the history of libraries, information professionals, and publishing in Ireland.

The Documentation Movement

The Irish Association for Documentation (IAD) was established in 1947 and later renamed as Irish Association for Documentation and Information Services in 1967. In the 1948 Annual Report, it was stated that the IAD wished to be part of the community of the International Federation for Documentation (FID). They made an application to the Department of External Affairs for a grant in aid of £200 per annum in 1947-48, but ultimately the IAD was not affiliated to the FID due to financial considerations.

Documentation, or the Documentation Movement, is commonly attributed to the “Brussels Institute” founded by Paul Otlet and Henry La Fontaine. They established the International Institute of Bibliography (IIB) as a universal centre of knowledge in Belgium in the late 19th

century and developed the Universal Decimal Classification (UDC). The IIB became the International Institute of Documentation in 1931. In the *Congres Mondial de La Documentation Universelle* in Paris in 1937 hosted by the International Institute of International Cooperation of the League of Nations, it was renamed as International Federation of Documentation (FID) (Murra 1951). IIB was an ambitious endeavour to collect and organise all knowledge for retrieval. Otlet's magnum opus, *Traité de Documentation* (1934), imagined a world where one can access information from their desk. The pioneering ideas had a major influence in the development of special libraries in Europe, especially the use of subject indexes and UDC.

In Great Britain, the Association of Special Libraries and Information Bureaux (ASLIB) was established in 1924 and the British Society of International Bibliography in 1927. Their proceedings showed the challenges of scientific and technical information faced by research and development in agriculture and industry, as well as academic inquiry in universities and research institutions ('Documentation' 2026). The need for abstracting and indexing periodicals arose alongside a demand for information services in science and technology. S. C. Bradford, who built the largest collection of scientific and technical periodicals during his tenure in the Science Library at South Kensington, often lamented the wasteful repetition of previous research because of limited or inefficient information access (see, for example, Bradford 1928). Questions about abstracting, classifying and indexing periodicals subsequently led to the Royal Society Scientific Information Conference in 1948. The High Commissioner for Eire was the representative of Ireland in this important conference ('List of Delegates' 1948).

The Inception of the Irish Association for Documentation

Established in 1947, the Irish Association for Documentation was a latecomer to the documentation movement. The Annual Reports 1948-1951 provide a glimpse of their activities and challenges in its early formation. Further studies can illuminate their rationale and ambition if more documentary evidence emerges in the future.

The Director of the National Library of Ireland at the time, Richard Hayes, attended the 16th meeting of the International Federation for Documentation in Paris in November 1946. He received assurances that the formation of an Irish branch would be welcomed and the proposal was supported by the British, Swiss, Dutch and other delegates. The Irish Association for Documentation was formed at a meeting on 4th July 1947 at a meeting held in the Royal Irish

Academy, attended by representatives from universities, the government, and learned and technical libraries and institutions. Its stated aim was “to promote in Ireland the recording, organisation and dissemination of specialised knowledge” (‘Annual Report 1948-1951’).

In the first Council meeting, Professor F. E. Hackett was appointed as Chair, Dr Richard Hayes as Honorary Secretary, and Miss C. Keogh as Honorary Treasurer. Professor Hackett was also the President of the Library Association of Ireland at the time (Lunney 2009). Four committees were appointed in the first Council meeting: (1) Committee for Science and Agriculture, (2) Committee for History and Archaeology, (3) Committee for Documentary Reproduction, and (4) Committee for Medicine. Ambitious plans were made by all four committees. While the Committee for Documentary Reproduction made plans to investigate photographic facilities and microphotography, the other three committees were to compile lists of periodicals in their respective knowledge domains. A common objective was to co-ordinate the collection of periodicals to avoid unnecessary duplication and improve information access.

The compilation of lists of periodicals, or what Bradford (1930) describes as the “Union Catalogue movement”, was deemed as a necessity for libraries of all kinds. Union catalogues had been published in America, Australia, France, Germany, Norway, South Africa, Switzerland since the 1920s, and the British Museum started publishing the *World List of Scientific Periodicals* in 1931. When the Irish Association was formed, there was no union list or catalogue of scientific periodicals in Ireland. It was felt that there is an urgent need to create and compile such tools to facilitate the dissemination of specialised knowledge, especially in the scientific and technical fields. In the process of compiling these lists, it was revealed that a large proportion of scientific materials was only available in Belfast and that many scientific periodicals required for research were not available in any Irish library (‘Annual Report 1948-1951’).

In the three years following the first Council meeting, the work of compilation proved challenging since it depended heavily on voluntary assistance. In 1951, it was reported that “the activities of the Association have been on a restricted scale during the year because of shortage of staff in the National Library” (‘Annual Report 1948-1951’). The first edition of the *Union List of Current Periodicals* in Dublin Libraries was published in 1954, and the second edition in 1960. Both were compiled in the National Library of Ireland for the Irish Association for Documentation. The contributing libraries of the 1960 edition includes: Central Statistics Office, Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, Foras Taluntais (The Agricultural Institute), Institute for Industrial Research

and Standards, Medical Research Council of Ireland, National Library of Ireland, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Royal Dublin Society, Royal Irish Academy, Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin, and Veterinary College of Ireland.

Irish Association for Documentation and Information Services, 1967-?

The title of the Association was altered to include “Information Services” in 1967. The reasons were not given in the short communication in *An Leabharlann* (‘Irish Association for Documentation and Information Services (iadis)’ 1968). By that time, the *Union List of Current Periodicals in Dublin Libraries* had been published periodically. Most importantly, the *Manuscript Sources for the History of Irish Civilisation*, an eleven-volume catalogue edited by Richard Hayes was published in 1965. While the undertaking of the *Manuscript Sources* was attributed to the Irish Association for Documentation, Hayes articulated the plans in 1960 in an article, “The Irish National Bibliography”, which describes the ambitious scope of the volumes.

There were few records about the Association in the years since 1951. One exception is the Annual Report for the year ending 31st March 1969, which showed a different organisation than its earlier years. There were four panels: (1) The Education and Training Panel, (2) Irish National Bibliography Panel, (3) Periodical Panel, and (4) Reproductive Services Panel. These panels were no longer organised by knowledge domains but organised by functions. Nevertheless, the objects of the Association remained: to improve the organisation and dissemination of information. One significant undertaking was the compilation of the *Irish Publishing Record* under the leadership of Ellen Power, University College Dublin.

In her “Introduction to *Irish Publishing Record, 1967*”, Power (1969) explained that Irish publications had been automatically recorded in the *British National Bibliography (BNB)* since 1950, but it was found that the *BNB* omitted many Irish titles. The conclusion was that Ireland could and should not rely on the *BNB* or sources outside of Ireland to list publications by Irish publishers. Based on her report, the Irish Association for Documentation made a recommendation to set up a Council regarding the publication of a National List in 1962. The list of titles received in the National Library of Ireland was published in *An Leabharlann* 1964-1967, and a new publication entitled *Irish Publishing Record* was to be compiled starting in the year of 1967. The first volume was put together by the students in the School of Librarianship, University College Dublin. The *Irish Publishing Record* was published annually between 1967 and 1994.

The addition of “information services” to the title of the Association reflects the changing nature of the profession. While the compilation of union lists and national bibliography was significant endeavours, the Association also started offering training in information services. Materials of the I.A.D.I.S. Course on Information Presentation and Dissemination Methods held on March 13-14, 1969, can be found in the National Library of Ireland’s collection. The course pack includes presentations about “Presenting your information in anticipation of demand” and “Assessing user needs”. The course was attended by 36 people from commerce and industry, government departments, state sponsored bodies, trade unions, colleges, universities and public libraries (‘Annual Report 1969’).

The Irish Association for Documentation and Information Services was still active in the 1970s. They published *Ireland and Irishmen in the American War of Independence: Some Historical Documents* in 1976, and a piece of IADIS News issued in 1977 can be found. However, these clues cannot tell us more about the activities of the Association in the 1970s and onwards, or when the Association ceased to operate. Even though the *Irish Publishing Record* was realised until 1994, there were only a few mentions of the Association in the volumes published in the late 1960s.

Conclusion

The Irish Association for Documentation was an important development in the history of library and information professionals in Ireland. The publications of the *Manuscript Sources for the History of Irish Civilisation* and *Irish Publishing Record* speak to the aspirations and ambition of documenting Ireland’s cultural, historical and scientific outputs. The brief history also shows us a glimpse of the development of the library and information profession in Ireland. It is hoped that more materials about the Association may exist, and I hope this research would stimulate interests in Irish library history.

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